

Appendix 2: A brief history of institutionalizing engineering ethics in the Netherlands¹

The 20th century witnessed various debates in the fields of ethics, technology, and engineering in the small country of the Netherlands. Before World War I started, the first professional societies and codes of conduct appeared in the Netherlands. Some events during this war, such as the use of chemical weapons, raised concerns in the scientific community about the possibility of misuse of science. After the war, lectures on science and society were held, and articles were published in both scientific and non-scientific outlets. With the beginning of World War II and the dropping of the American nuclear bomb on Japan, these concerns continued, leading to the establishment of labor-union-like societies for scientists such as VVO and BWA to pay attention to scientists' social responsibilities (Rip & Boeker, 1975).

During the 1950s and 1960s, these societies and industrial companies, such as Philips, held conferences and lectures on social responsibility and moral values. In 1960, the Higher Education Act formally requested universities to pay attention to their social responsibilities. However, according to Rip and Boeker (1975), the universities did not truly adhere to or comply with this request in their academic practices.

The 1970s saw criticism of science and technology. For instance, the Club of Rome's publication of the Limits to Growth report had profound implications for various parts of Europe, including the Netherlands. It presented predictions about growth, pollution, and resource management, marking instances where environmental issues were addressed as consequential to technological advancements. The report challenged the previously optimistic assumption that every new scientific and technological development benefits individuals and society. According to Grunwald (2014), this re-evaluation of the dual nature of technology, recognizing its ambivalence, contributed to triggering a crisis of orientation in approaching science and technology. This crisis, in turn, played a crucial role in motivating the emergence of Technology Assessment (TA). During this period, public concerns about developing technologies like microelectronics, including personal computers, prompted the establishment of advisory committees such as the Rathenau Commission. The ethical aspects of technologies were also discussed at scientific conferences. These initiatives were sufficient for the Dutch Parliament to pass several acts that regulated the use of technology (Kool et al., 2017). In academic education, courses (often compulsory) and

¹ This text is an appendix of the paper "A Comparative Institutional Analysis of Engineering Ethics in the Netherlands and the United States".

seminars on the ethical and social aspects of science and technology were included in the engineering education curricula (Zandvoort et al., 2000).

This trend of establishing initiatives to investigate technology's social and ethical aspects continued in the 1980s. Along with the emergence of advisory committees and commissions in the government, larger organizations such as NOTA were established to study science and technology's social and moral effects to inform the government (Kool et al., 2017). Another example is the VWW, which was launched in 1980 and published the *Journal of Science, Technology, and Society* (Boers, 1981). Since this decade, the work of Dutch researchers has played an important international role in advancing ethics and technology studies. Also, in professional societies, the first codes of ethics appeared in this decade (Brumsen, 2005) and continued in the next decade.

The most crucial event in the 1990s was the legislation of the Higher Education and Research Act in 1993 on the report of NOTA, in which universities were asked to "pay attention to personal development and the promotion of societal responsibility" (Brumsen, 2005). In response to this Act, the board of TU Delft, the largest and oldest university of technology in the Netherlands, established the Advisory Committee on Ethics (ACE) to prepare recommendations for ethics education for engineering students. This committee presented its recommendations to the university board and, after approval, delivered the result to the Department of Philosophy in that university for implementation (Scheurwater & Doorman, 2001). In 1996, the teaching of ethics courses started at this university, and the department organized a series of workshops, seminars, and conferences to support these courses. After TU Delft, two other universities of technology in the Netherlands, namely Twente (UT) and Eindhoven (TU/e) universities, also began establishing ethics courses and research (van de Poel et al., 2001). These universities have implemented projects to develop education and research in recent years. TU Delft organized an international Research in Ethics and Engineering conference in April 2002 (Brumsen, 2005).

In professional organizations, the KNCV and the KIVI-NIRIA, the largest professional associations, published their codes of conduct in 1997 and 2003, respectively. According to a study conducted in 1999, about forty percent of the companies in the country had an ethical code of conduct (Brumsen, 2005). In 1993, a report commissioned by the Ministry of Education and Science in the Netherlands addressed professional codes in the technical sciences. The study suggested the development of an advisory professional code specifically for engineers. Subsequently, the Ministry sought feedback from the Bèta Federation, the umbrella organization representing major technical and scientific professional associations in the country. However, the Beta Federation declined to

collaborate on a joint initiative, asserting that the responsibility to formulate a code, if deemed necessary, rested with individual professional associations (van de Poel, 2004).

The field experienced a stormy development in the Netherlands in the 2000s (van de Poel, 2010). The development of ethics and technology studies continued in the 2000s and 2010s. Various research projects were carried out with the support of governmental and non-governmental organizations. The three technical universities—TU Delft, Eindhoven University of Technology (TU/e), and the University of Twente (UT)—defined several research projects. To facilitate further cooperation, they collectively established the 3TU. Ethics Centre, the largest center in the world dedicated to the ethics of technology, in 2007 (van de Poel, 2010). Several programs defined by the Dutch research council (NWO) strengthened this center in the field of ethics and technology, such as Information Technology and Ethics (1995), Ethics of Technological Research (2003), and Socially Responsible Innovation (2009) (van de Poel, 2010). The last one started with the participation of the NWO and six ministries. By defining various projects and organizing consecutive conferences since 2011, this program created a platform that has become a constant place for responsible innovation researchers, policy, and scientific centers (Van Den Hoven, 2014).

After many years of development, the Netherlands is now seen as one of the best places in the world for ethics and technology, also called engineering ethics.